
THE EFFECT OF TRADE BRANDS ON PURCHASE DECISIONS ON HONDA MOTORS IN PT ABADI MOTOR INDONESIA

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Abstract:

Trademarks will be a source of competitiveness that can last a long time and can be a producer of cash flow for the company in the long run. Products that have strong brands will be difficult to imitate because consumers' perceptions of value or certain brands will not be easy to create. Brands are signs in the form of images, names, words, letters, numbers of color arrangements, or a combination of these elements which has a distinguishing power and is used in the trading of goods and services. Whereas purchasing decisions are a process of integration that combines knowledge to evaluate two or more alternative behaviors and choose one of them. The method in this study uses the field reserch method to obtain primary data in the form of observations, interviews and questionnaires and the library reserch method to obtain secondary data in the form of library data from scientific works, thesis, thesis, dissertation and books relevant to the research title. The purpose of this research is to find out whether there is a trademark influence on purchasing decisions of Honda motorcycles. The results of his research are: For simple linear regression analysis the results are: $b = 0.43$, $a = 18.28$, then $Y = 18.28 + 0.43 X$. Correlation Test, the result: $r = 0.56$. The results of the coefficient of determination analysis = $r^2 = 31.36\%$. Hypothesis testing is to find out the significance of the trademark influence on purchasing decisions, namely the results t count = 2.866, as for t table with an error rate of 5% (0.05) sample of 20 people and the result is t table = 2.101, then t count is greater than t table then H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected, which means there is a significant influence between the trademark on the purchase decision of Honda motorcycles at PT Abadi motor, Indonesia.

Keywords: Trade Mark; Purchase Decision.

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1. Introduction

In this day and age, where many people use transportation to meet their daily needs, where many transportation means people choose to use motorbikes to go to work, business, or other necessities, because nowadays there are traffic jams so the use of motorcycles faster and more efficient. Even now motorcycles can be used as online jobs so that they become new jobs, thus encouraging people to buy motorbikes at the best price and quality, of course this is seen from the brand, quality, model, agile, economical, and high after-sales.

Today there are many different types of motorbikes that have been produced by well-known companies such as Honda, Yamaha, Suzuki, Kawasaki, and Vespa, with various motorcycle models such as: motorcycle, motorbike, road bike, motor sport, offroad motorbike, etc. Of course, this makes consumers have many choices to buy it.

Seeing the reality on the streets and parking lots turned out to be the most Honda brands. Honda brand motorcycles are one of the most sought after products by consumers and even more have one to meet their daily needs.

People buy motorbikes now more easily because the advertisements are intense both through print media and electronic media, and motorbike sales on the streets distribute brochures, in crowded places there are many motorbikes displaying various types of motorbikes, besides that which tempts consumers with DP Rp. 500,000 and photos of copies of Identity cards and family cards can already be used for motorcycle.

At present the competition between motorcycle brands is getting sharper both from the design of their products, prices, models, colors, quality, efficiency, speed and ease of purchase, besides advertising is also very influential consumers to buy it.

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psychological. For consumers, the brand impression inherent in a product is called a brand image.

Brands are one of the important factors in marketing activities because the activities of introducing and offering products and services cannot be separated from reliable brands. This means that the brand does not stand alone. Brands must be in accordance with the components of other marketing processes (Surachman, 2008: 1). In addition, understanding the brand is not just something that can display its functional value, but also can provide a certain value in the hearts of consumers (Surachman, 2008: 2).

Brands have several roles for companies that market them, namely their role is the role of the economy and strategic role. The important role of the economy is to enable companies to achieve economies of scale by producing these brands in bulk. The other invaluable role of the economy is that successful brands can be a barrier for competitors who want to introduce the same brand. Brands have an important strategic role by being a differentiator between the products offered by a company and rival brands (Kanuk, 2008: 123).

The second dimension of knowledge about brands based on consumers (consumer based brand knowledge) is the image of a brand. Brand image can be considered as a type of association that arises in the minds of consumers when remembering a particular brand. The association can simply appear in the form of certain thoughts or images associated with a brand. This association can be conceptualized based on type, support, strength, and uniqueness. Types of brand associations include attributes, benefits, and attitudes. Attributes consist of attributes related to the product such as design, color, size and attributes not related to the product, for example the price, user and image of use.

The brand itself is basically used for several purposes, namely:

- 1) As an identity, which is useful in differentiating or distinguishing a company's products from its competitors' products.
- 2) Promotional tools, as a product attraction.
- 3) To foster an image by giving confidence, assurance, and certain prestige to consumers.
- 4) To control the market.

Brands have an important role in marketing. There is a considerable difference between products and brands. The product is just something that is produced in a factory and easily imitated, while brand is something that consumers buy and always has a uniqueness that is difficult to imitate (Tjiptono, 2008; 105).

Brand elements, namely: Name, Logo, Symbol, Design, Slogan and packaging. This means that the brand is a sign in the form of an image, name, word, letters, numbers, arrangement of colors or a combination of these elements.

Brand Benefits

Brands are beneficial to producers according to Tjiptono, 2011: 43 namely:

- 1) Identification means to facilitate the process of handling or tracking products for companies, especially in organizing inventory and accounting records.
- 2) A form of legal protection against unique features or aspects of the product.
- 3) Signal quality level for satisfied customers, so they can easily choose and buy it again at a later time.

- 4) Means create associations and unique meanings to differentiate products from competitors.
- 5) The source of positive excellence, especially through legal protection, customer loyalty, and unique images formed in the minds of consumers.
- 6) Sources of financial returns primarily involve future income.

According to Tjiptono (2011: 44) the potential functions of a brand include identification, practicality, guarantee, organization, characterization, continuity, hedonistic, and ethical functions. Meanwhile grouping the benefits of the brand into three categories: rarity (economic benefits or value for money), virtosity (functional benefits (functional or quality benefits) and complecibility (psychological benefits or personal satisfaction) Ambar, 2000 in Tjiptono (2011: 44).

Things that are closely related to the brand

- 1) Brand name, which is a part of a brand that can be pronounced or pronounced. For example: Hond, Toyota, Pepsodent, Aqua, and others.
- 2) Brand mark, which is part of a recognizable brand, but cannot be read or pronounced> This brand mark is a logo, symbol, color, image, design.
- 3) Brand characteristics to be a potential brand:

- A Quality Product

Since consumer satisfaction is used to measure brand values, quality is the number one that consumers want.

- Being First

Being the first in the market, not in technology

- Unique Positioning Concept

The brand must have a unique concept position, which will distinguish it from its competitors.

- Strong Communication Program

Successful brands must be accompanied by effective sales, advertising, promotional campaigns that will communicate the functions of the brand and the values contained in it.

- Time and Consistency

Brands are not built in a fast time, it takes time to build the brand and the values in it. And maintaining mefek values requires continuous time continuously and is associated with environmental change.

2. Purchasing Decisions

According to Peter and Olson (2010: 417) argue that purchasing decisions are a process of integration that combines knowledge to evaluate two or more alternative behaviors and choose one of them. The decision to buy can lead to various processes in making these decisions. The purchase decision is a process where the consumer will decide to buy the product or not. Consumer decisions to buy a product, when the consumer has thought about whether or not it is appropriate to buy the product, by considering the various kinds of information that consumers know about the reality of the product when consumers witness firsthand.

According to Kotler in Fandy Tjiptono (2008: 20) in consumer purchasing decisions there are often more than two parties from the exchange or purchase process. For example there are five kinds of

roles that can be performed by someone. There are times when these five roles are held by one person, but often these roles are carried out by several people. An understanding of this role is very useful in order to satisfy the needs and desires of consumers. The five roles include:

- 1) Pemrakarsa is the person who first menyarankan buy a product or service.
- 2) The giver of influence is the person who views or advises weight in the final decision making.
- 3) Decision making is the person who determines most or all of the purchasing decisions, whether the buyer, what is bought, when to buy, how to buy, and where to buy.
- 4) Users are people who consume or use products or services.

- Steps to Purchase Decisions

Consumers in making decisions also know the process, before they buy a product from a particular company, so that the purchasing decision does not feel disappointed when they have bought a product.

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2008: 234) argue that the decision-making process is an approach to problem solving divided into 5 stages, namely:

- 1) Introduction to the Problem.

Identifying these desires and needs is shown primarily to recognize the existence of desires and needs that have not been fulfilled and have not been satisfied.

- 2) Information Search

Consumers who are inspired by their needs will be encouraged to seek more information about the products or services they need. Information seeking can be active or passive. Active information in the form of visits to several stores, to compare prices and product quality. While passive information, by reading an advertisement in a magazine or newspaper without having a specific purpose and rationale about the description of the desired product.

- 3) Alternative Evaluation

This stage includes two stages, namely determining the purpose of purchase and assessing and holding a section on alternative purchases based on the purpose of the purchase.

- 4) Purchasing Decisions.

The decision to buy here is a real form of purchase. When consumers decide to buy, consumers will meet a series of decisions that must be made regarding the type of product, brand, seller, quantity, time of purchase, and method of purchase.

- 5) Post-Purchase Behavior.

After consumers buy a product, consumers will feel satisfaction or dissatisfaction.

Factors that influence purchasing decisions

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2008: 235), purchasing decision factors consist of:

1) Cultural Factors

Cultural factors have a wide and profound influence on consumer behavior. This factor consists of: culture, sub-culture, and social class.

2) Social Factors

In addition to cultural factors, consumer behavior is also influenced by social factors such as reference groups, families and social status.

3) Personal Factors.

Personal factors that contribute to consumer behavior consist of age and life cycle stages, work and economic environment, lifestyle, personality, and self-concept.

4) Psychological factors

The choice of one's purchase is influenced by four main psychological factors, namely: motivation, perception, learning, and beliefs and convictions.

3. Research Methods

Research place at Honda motorcycle dealers ... in Bekasi, Indonesia, research time for 1 month in December 2018. The method in this study uses the field reserch method to obtain primary data in the form of observations, interviews and questionnaire distribution and library reserch methods to obtain secondary data in the form of library data from scientific works, thesis, thesis, dissertation and books relevant to the research title. The purpose of the study was to find out whether there was a trademark influence on purchasing decisions of Honda motorcycles at dealerships PT. Abadi Motor Indonesia, and how much influence?, the independent variable was a trademark and the dependent variable was a purchasing decision.

The research instruments used were questionnaires to prospective buyers of Honda brand motorcycles for 1 month with a sample of 25 people with random sampling techniques, data processing from the answers to the collected questionnaires that had been filled out by respondents and the data was processed by statistical formula namely simple linear regression test , test the correlation, test the coefficient of determination and hypothesis testing.

4. Research Results

In the results of this study the data obtained through the questionnaire then discussed the data obtained from 20 respondents after being processed with a Likert scale, which was taken randomly. The results are: $\sum X = 573$, $\sum Y = 609$, $\sum X^2 = 17,231$, $\sum Y^2 = 19,023$, $\sum XY = 17,800$. For simple linear regression analysis the results are: $b = 0.43$, $a = 18.28$, then $Y = 18.28 + 0.43 X$.

The results of the Simple Correlation Regression analysis are to find out how much the calculation of the correlation coefficient from the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, the result: $r = 0.56$. The results of the analysis of the determination coefficient, namely the results of correlation analysis can be continued by calculating the coefficient of determination, namely the calculated r value is squared and multiplied by 100%, $KD = r^2 \cdot 100\% = 31.36\%$. Hypothesis testing is to find out the significance of the trademark influence on purchasing decisions, namely the result of t count = 2.866,

as for t table with an error rate of 5% (0.05) sample of 20 people and the result is t table = 2.101, then t count is greater than t table then H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected which means there is a significant influence between trademarks on motor purchasing decisions Honda at PT Abadi Motor, Indonesia

5. Conclusions and Suggestions

Conclude

After processing and analyzing the data collected through statistical tests, the conclusions are as follows:

- The results of simple linear regression analysis are $a = 18.28$ and $b = 0.43$. From the results of simple linear regression analysis, the equation $Y = 18.28 + 0.43 X$, where the rise and fall of the value of Y is strongly influenced by the value of X .
- The results of the product moment correlation coefficient analysis (r) from the statistical calculation obtained $r = 0.56$, which means that the trademark influence on the purchase decision of a Honda motorbike at PT ... Bekasi is positive and strong.
- The results of the Coefficient of Determination (KD) amounted to 31.36%, meaning that it can be seen that trademarks influence purchasing decisions by 31.36%, the remaining 68.64% is influenced by other variables not included in this study.
- In testing the hypothesis obtained the value of t count of 2.866 greater than t table 2.101 with an error rate of 5% (0.05) this means that according to the provisions of the hypothesis test the results are H_a accepted and H_0 rejected

Advice

Based on the results of these studies, the researchers suggest the following:

- Maintain the good name of the company by providing satisfying services to consumers with quality products, affordable prices, and product guarantees, which will influence purchasing decisions.
- Establish a good relationship with consumers so that one day they will buy back or the consumer will invite other consumers to buy the product.

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